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Addiction of Slavery

A Brief Critique on Modern Society

Part 1

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In the modern course of time philosophy of society in terms of common people is encountering with serious violent attacks from worthless literates and even illiterate arrogant lumpens. This note is therefore truly essential to educate people about the glory of values and works in human life. The worse tendency of modern culture is the colonization of fear which consequently gives brutal nasty treatment and results in severe violence and deaths of thousand innocent sons. This great foolish act engulfs almost all people of all class especially my labours, peasants and farmers and other workers whom I will generally call as "The Engine of Humanistic Society" the supremacy of this addiction is absolute slavery, the dangerous facets of civilization. Majority of leaders are the vector of such activities and they in any ruling form needs to be overthrown with severe attention. The self requirement of human beings must only be fulfilled by work and must never by addiction of slavery or

political blessings. The degree of infections occurred in humanistic organs and organizations are massive. The best reward as a consequence of this nasty truth is frustration due to up rise of continuous slavery which nowadays a major socio economic problems. The road to people's alliance is the perfect way towards absolute wit and unprecedented display of bravery which must initialize only to decimate the rotten minds of independent nation(s). The farmer's demand is our top and supreme top priority and needs to be visualized as hard as emergency circumstances. An army of farmers typically acts a crucial weapon of living, and employment solely owned by state must belong to all means each and every of my common friends of all class mostly to them whom we are dependent in all possible occasions. To avoid severe economic collapse or depression, movements of comrades must rise in front of capital buildings in Capital City. The foundation

of disciplined youths must wave flags of liberty and for their rights and each and every youth must be educated in terms of mathematical economics and its absolute and daily common and universal applications. The study of science, medical science and philosophical implications as well as disciplines and decorum are more important for the existence of peaceful civilization, the strength of society must rise in terms of humanistic ideologies completely and heavily equipped with scientific knowledge, inspirations and courage to put forward new ideas well structured with logics and derivations. Peoples of all class must study the advancement of science in their own language and must boil it down as simple as possible and must express their views on it. Poor beggars must enroll themselves in developing technical skills which needs to be improved and even recreate new techniques which will prove fruitful in near future for country's development through well

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employment and training youths with highest degree of encouragement and motivations. Every single friend is a honorable asset and treasure for nation; no single people must be hungry all will have to work and employment power needs the form of pure accuracy and every single must be offered a glorious chance to show their skills. If anyone does not able to show the proper then temporary funds must ensure for them and must be trained by educated officials and then they needs to be equipped with work of permanent position. The state must show respect of highest order to all assets including my very backward brothers and sisters. Victory must be seriously achieved by the means of truths and the skills of workers immortal arms. Democracy is for each and for all; all are equal in front of nature's balance one needs to preserve it by realistic means through peace. If we cannot provide breads to a single people that simple means the beginning of great loss of our very own pride and it's time not to cry but to must rescue and stabilize at any cost but in peace in order to avoid great falling of economic

and democratic pillars. All friends needs to donate and must share among others in order to exist the real distinguished values of humanity. The sectors of employment and economic establishments must only and only be owned by state and all single workers are our organs to preserve democracy and to dethrone the addiction of severe slavery. All peoples must suggest their best opinions and they must be armed with fruitful ideas, thoughts and spirits of continuation and encouragements. In this system the controller of states does not only have power to alter its rules, our highly skilled working labors and farmers must make proposals to change something which will harm democracy. The plans will be discussed publicly and will be revised by all working class and established it as a law for the betterment of humanity. Vision of all friends must be treated as top and supreme priority and must be rewarded with great pride of highest honor. Not a single people must be left unemployed in this regime of bright society. Beggar free civilization, employed civilization, scientific civilization, disciplined youthful

civilization, defeating backward by work, education, skills and love is the only road to discard the evil slavery and to declare that each of us is the immortal hands of eternal democratic arena. To run the engine of the civilized society in a highest order of extreme smoothness we need to transform the entire rotten image and frame the new economic and scientific theories based on only practical way the people are behaving and not hypothetically. The advancement in state must upgrade as per new breakthroughs and discoveries in each and every possible field. Educations must generate great opportunity for each and every people of all class including farmer's son and my backward poor friends we must treat them with highest priority regardless of their financial sufferings. There must neither be rich nor poor all will be equal and all must work to enjoy the fruits and nature's beauty in the form of "love for humanity". The state under this system must ensure to destroy and burn the nasty roots of poisonous financial pain of all as discussed earlier. The crucial nasty achievement in

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modern society is law; it is very complex to determine whether the laws are for the common people or against them. We do believe that protector and judge is absolute slaves of government for this reason they needs to be treated with supreme priority. Laws of lumpens colonized our society as if it is the "Land of Bright Evils" their death must occur through the rise of conscience of humanity. Government officers and administrative offices and the government itself in modern society are nasty and behave as if they are termites and angry donkey. The root of plagiarism infects all humanistic arenas and decimates the common talent and taste of my friends. The laws needs radical and intense modification based on scientific pillars enriched with wit and new knowledge and its protector must be all not only the state alone. The common people must decide the mechanisms of the society, it is very crucial to overthrow and decimate the profound roots of so called "Fragment Rule Policy by National Laws" or "Dirty Land of Pressurized Slaves". This modern fashion of slavery has become a ruthless tradition of society

and our motto must be to ruin this facet of society. Unscientific activities or rules and framework in any sector must be discarded without mercy. The identity of any workers, peoples must be only human being and not caste, religion, country, or any other criteria. We should treat them with highest image of humanity. The basic motivation for scientific education is the creativity enriched with philosophical ideas and inspirations and examples and science must not and never be done due to military or government pressures but as independent advancement. We will not be blind and always demand enriched and scientifically valid evidence for each and every occurrence. We need to create "Humanistic Unification of All Soldiers" in independent state, here soldiers signifies each and every people's strength. This modern society is currently in the form which can be described in one line written by Shakespeare, "Sans Taste, Sans Eyes and Sans Everything"

The natural decay of so called "society of lumpens" and "addiction of slavery" will only be possible if we educate ourselves with this

discussed brief ideologies. The philosophical dream of G.W.Von Leibniz is that, good will ultimately prevails because one needs to remember, speaking strictly, democracy will lose its greatness or will became senseless if there will be no human or humanity or if we root out our honor towards delicate pillars I mean poor arms and poor kids . We need to be highly optimistic and needs to peacefully construct the "Optimum Lustrous Democratic Stage" In this modern version of society workers and my poor comrades are being treated as similar to wild creatures and even daily mass killing. This lumpens are murderers and they needs to be demolished. This deleterious vision is due to lout, megalomaniac and disdainful rulers or frivolous creatures and they are ruthlessly and brutally killing the hands of society and setting the engine on an indefinite freeze. We do believe that the nightmare and apocalyptic forever end of this nastiest and cruel society (not society after all) is on its way. The school of democracy needs to be established and must create an atmosphere like lyceum. We need a revolution of, strictly speaking, disciplined

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youthquake for the preservation of the highest form of people's power and should establish an entirely new image and form of society which will be beyond imagination for many termites currently in action in this nasty form. We must place our ethics first rather than any theoretical study of hypothetical form. The laws must be authoritative and excellent in its true form based on scientific wisdoms and science cultivation. This modern society should and must needs to be ruined and completely abolished.

If you believe in illusion then you must believe in God, but if you interpret it enriched in scientific wisdom then you must discard God and dethrone slavery. There is nothing to smile and nothing to be proud for any nation if it cannot provide biscuits, breads and rice to even a single of its son and daughter. Criticisms based on scientific mind are welcome but must be constructive and shall explain its treatment.

Originally written to teach the purest form of reality and to encourage minds to study science using thoughts and independent thinking and they must foreword their ideas for the benefit of

mankind. Each and every people are talented and can able to progress our beautiful society if they work based on science and melodious chants by ignoring other hopeless experiences and meaningless activities.